

1 **Intramammary infections and risk factors in freshly calved heifers in dairy herds**

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8 Supplementary Table 1. Numbers (%) of bacterial findings in udder quarter colostrum samples, milk samples from day 3-4 after calving and all
9 colostrum/milk samples collected from 722 freshly calved heifers in herds with a large proportion of first parity cows with low SCC at first and
10 second milk recording after calving (LL herds, n=9), a large proportion of first parity cows with high SCC at first milk recording and low SCC at
11 the second milk recording (HL herds, n=9) or a large proportion of first parity cows with high SCC at first and second milk recording (HH herds,
12 n=7) after calving

Finding	Colostrum				Milk day 3-4				All			
	LL	HL	HH	Total	LL	HL	HH	Total	LL	HL	HH	Total
No growth	573 (53)	506 (48)	323 (43)	1402 (49)	616 (59)	581 (59)	393 (55)	1590 (58)	1189 (56)	1087 (54)	716 (49)	2992 (54)
Contamination	331 (31)	383 (37)	276 (37)	990 (35)	313 (30)	281 (29)	213 (30)	807 (30)	644 (31)	664 (33)	489 (33)	1797 (32)
<i>Specific infection</i>	168 (16)	156 (15)	148 (20)	472 (16)	107 (10)	115 (12)	110 (15)	332 (12)	275 (13)	271 (13)	258 (18)	804 (14)
<i>S. chromogenes</i>	97 (9)	66 (6)	74 (10)	237 (8)	66 (6)	51 (5)	54 (8)	171 (6)	163 (8)	117 (6)	128 (9)	408 (7)
<i>S. aureus</i>	17 (2)	16 (2)	22 (3)	55 (2)	13 (1)	17 (2)	19 (3)	49 (2)	30 (1)	33 (2)	41 (3)	104 (2)
<i>S. hemolyticus</i>	6 (0.6)	20 (2)	9 (1)	35 (1)	8 (0.8)	9 (0.9)	3 (0.4)	20 (0.7)	14 (0.7)	29 (1)	12 (0.8)	55 (1)
<i>S. simulans</i>	5 (0.5)	5 (0.5)	10 (1)	20 (0.7)	6 (0.6)	9 (0.9)	17 (2)	32 (1)	11 (0.5)	14 (0.7)	27 (2)	52 (0.9)
<i>Str. dysgalactiae</i>	7 (0.7)	9 (0.9)	8 (1)	24 (0.8)	2 (0.2)	5 (0.5)	2 (0.3)	9 (0.3)	9 (0.4)	14 (0.7)	10 (0.7)	33 (0.6)
<i>S. epidermidis</i>	4 (0.4)	9 (0.9)	3 (0.4)	16 (0.6)	0 (0)	8 (0.8)	4 (0.6)	12 (0.4)	4 (0.2)	18 (0.8)	7 (0.5)	28 (0.5)

<i>S. hyicus</i>	13 (1)	3 (0.3)	3 (0.4)	19 (0.7)	4 (0.4)	5 (0.5)	2 (0.3)	11 (0.4)	17 (0.8)	8 (0.4)	5 (0.3)	30 (0.5)
<i>S. sciuri</i>	3 (0.3)	0 (0)	5 (0.7)	8 (0.3)	0 (0)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.1)	4 (0.2)	3 (0.1)	3 (0.1)	6 (0.4)	12 (0.2)
<i>S. capitis</i>	3 (0.3)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.1)	7 (0.2)	1 (0.1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)	4 (0.2)	3 (0.2)	1 (0.1)	8 (0.1)
<i>Str. uberis</i>	0 (0)	2 (0.2)	2 (0.3)	4 (0.1)	1 (0.1)	0 (0)	2 (0.3)	3 (0.1)	1 (0.05)	2 (0.1)	4 (0.3)	7 (0.1)
<i>S. spp</i>	7 (0.7)	6 (0.6)	3 (0.4)	16 (0.6)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.1)	0 (0)	2 (0.1)	8 (0.4)	7 (0.4)	3 (0.2)	18 (0.3)
<i>Str. spp.</i>	1 (0.1)	0 (0)	1 (0.1)	2 (0.1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0.05)	0 (0)	1 (0.1)	2 (0.04)
<i>Enterococcus</i> spp.	0 (0)	0(0)	3 (0.4)	3 (0.1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0.1)	1 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (0.3)	4 (0.1)
<i>Lactococcus spp.</i>	2 (0.2)	2 (0.2)	0 (0)	4 (0.1)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.1)	0 (0)	2 (0.1)	3 (0.1)	3 (0.2)	0 (0)	6 (0.1)
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	0 (0)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.1)	2 (0.1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0.1)	1 (0)	9 (0)	1 (0.05)	2 (0.1)	3 (0.05)
Other agents	3 (0.3)	14 (1)	3 (0.4)	20 (0.7)	4 (0.4)	6 (0.6)	4 (0.6)	14 (0.5)	7 (0.3)	20 (1)	7 (0.5)	34 (0.6)
Total	1072	1045	747	2864	1036	977	716	2729	2108	2022	1463	5593

14 Supplementary Table 2. Number (%) of udder quarters with the same or different growth in
 15 milk samples from day 3-4 after calving as in colostrum samples collected from 568 freshly
 16 calved heifers, with udder quarters with specific infection or no growth, in 25 herds
 17 participating in a study on udder health of freshly calved heifers

Growth d 3-4	Growth in colostrum		Total	P-value
	No	Yes		
Any type of specific infection				<0.001
No	962 (94)	149 (48)	1111 (83)	
Yes	57 (6)	164 (52)	221 (17)	
Total	1019 (100)	314 (100)	1333 (100)	
<i>Staphylococcus chromogenes</i>				<0.001
No	962 (97)	69 (47)	1031 (91)	
Yes	28 (3)	78 (53)	106 (9)	
Total	990 (100)	147 (100)	1137 (100)	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>				<0.001
No	962 (99)	10 (24)	972 (96)	
Yes	7 (0.7)	31 (76)	38 (4)	
Total	969 (100)	41 (100)	1010 (100)	
<i>Staphylococcus hemolyticus</i>				<0.001
No	962 (99.6)	18 (75)	980 (99)	
Yes	4 (0.4)	6 (25)	10 (1)	
Total	966 (100)	24 (100)	990 (100)	
<i>Staphylococcus simulans</i>				0.05
No	962 (99)	3 (17)	965 (98)	
Yes	7 (0.7)	15 (83)	22 (2)	
Total	967 (100)	18 (100)	987 (100)	
<i>Streptococcus dysgalactiae</i>				na ¹
No	962 (100)	10 (71)	972 (99.6)	
Yes	0 (0)	4 (29)	4 (0.4)	
Total	962 (100)	14 (100)	976 (100)	
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>				na
No	962 (99.9)	2 (29)	964 (99)	
Yes	1 (0.1)	5 (71)	6 (1)	

Total	963 (100)	7 (100)	970 (100)	
<i>Staphylococcus hyicus</i>				<0.001
No	962 (99.9)	7 (64)	969 (99)	
Yes	1 (0.1)	4 (36)	5 (1)	
Total	963	11 (100)	974 (100)	
<i>Streptococcus uberis</i>				na
No	962 (100)	2 (66)	964 (99.9)	
Yes	0 (0)	1 (33)	1 (0.1)	
Total	962 (100)	3 (100)	965 (100)	

18 ¹na = not analyzed.

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21 Supplementary Table 3. Distribution of 132 bovine milk isolates of *Staphylococcus*
 22 *chromogenes* of different multi-locus sequence types (ST). The isolates originated in
 23 colostrum or milk from day 3-4 after calving in freshly calved heifers in 13 herds with at least
 24 3 milk isolates per herd

ST	Total number of isolates	Herds													Number of herds/ST
		A	E	G	I	K	S	X	Y	Z	Å	Ä	AB	AC	
1	8		1					2 ¹	2 ¹	1				2 ¹	5
6	23		3 ¹	10 ³		3 ¹			5 ¹			2 ¹			5
15	4	2							2						2
19	8				1			4 ²	2 ¹					1	4
28	2						2 ¹								1
38	1									1					1
43	1			1											1
44	2				2 ¹										1
48	3		3 ¹												1
62	1				1										1
69	2						2								1
99	3								1	2 ¹					2
100	4		2 ¹										2		2
102	5		2 ¹							1	2				3
104	1					1									1
108	1				1										1
109	9	1		1			1			5 ¹			1		5
113	4				4 ²										1
118	2				2										1
119	5			1									4 ¹		2
120	1	1													1
126	1											1			1
127	8							2 ¹	3 ¹					3	3
130	3					3 ¹									1
131	1							1							1

132	1									1					1
133	5										2 ¹	3 ¹			2
134	4										2 ¹	2 ¹			2
135	2												2 ¹		1
136	2													2 ¹	1
137	1													1	1
138	2													2 ¹	1
139	2						2 ¹								1
140	2							2 ¹							1
141	1												1		1
142	1					1									1
143	1					1									1
144	2						2 ¹								1
145	1					1									1
146	2													2 ¹	1
Total	132	4	11	13	11	10	9	11	15	11	6	8	10	13	
ST/ Herd		3	5	4	6	6	5	5	6	6	3	4	5	7	

25 ¹ The same ST was found in both colostrum and milk sample from the same udder quarter in
26 one freshly calved heifer.

27 ² The same ST was found in both colostrum and milk sample from the same udder quarter in
28 two freshly calved heifers.

29 ³ The same ST was found in both colostrum and milk sample from the same udder quarter in
30 four freshly calved heifers.

31 **Supplementary Figures 1-3**

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35 Supplementary Figure 1. Minimum spanning tree of whole genome MLST results of 132
36 bovine milk isolates (sample number) and 4 skin swab isolates (SOD) of *Staphylococcus*
37 *chromogenes* from 13 herds where each herd has a different colour. The size of the circle
38 indicates number of isolates. The numbers between circles indicate allele difference.

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43 Supplementary Figure 2. Whole genome MLST results from 18 bovine milk isolates of
 44 *Staphylococcus aureus* from 3 herds where each herd has a different colour. The size of the
 45 circle indicates number of isolates. The numbers in each circle represents ST number
 46 followed by cow number.

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49 Supplementary Figure 3. Minimum spanning tree of whole genome MLST results from 24
 50 bovine milk isolates and 21 skin swab samples (SOD) of *Staphylococcus hemolyticus* from 5
 51 herds where each herd has a different colour. The numbers between circles indicate allele
 52 difference.